

Research Article

EFFECT OF DIFFERENT SOLVENTS SYSTEM ON ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY AND PHYTOCHEMICAL SCREENING IN VARIOUS HABITATS OF *OCIMUM BASILICUM* L. (SWEET BASIL) LEAVES

M. Murali and G. Prabakaran*

PG & Research department of Botany, Government Arts College, Dharmapuri - 636 705, Tamilnadu, India.

Article History: Received 27th November 2017; Accepted 23rd April 2018; Published 29th September 2018

ABSTRACT

The present study is to screen the antioxidant activity and phytochemical constituents of different polar and non polar solvent such as methanol, acetone, Petroleum ether, chloroform and aqueous extracts of various geographic habitat *Ocimum basilicum* leaves. Soxhlet extraction of leaves was used to find the antioxidant activity performed using non enzymatic ABTS and enzymatic GPx assay. Based on the results of antioxidant content present in Basil leaves methanol extracts further study was made to find the qualitative phytochemical analysis, Thin Layer Chromatography and GC-MS. In the antioxidant activity determined by ABTS radical scavenging method the highest value was highest observed in the lowest concentration (0.5 mg/ml) of methanol and aqueous extracts 42.03 ± 0.05 and 41.96 ± 96 respectively in Chidambaram and Yercaud samples. Glutathione peroxidase least concentration (0.5 mg/ml) of aqueous extract from Ramanathapuram sample found to show the (176.26 ± 0.05 units/mg protein/min) highest activity. Phytochemical screening was performed to find the presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, terpenoids moderate concentrations, polyphenols, saponins, steroids and negative result glycosides and tannins. In GC-MS analysis qualitatively more than ten bioactive compounds were identified including Linalool, Caffeic acid etc. Results of the present study on *O. basilicum* has promising antioxidant activity and could serve as natural antioxidants.

Keywords: Antioxidant activity, ABTS, GPx, *Ocimum basilicum*, Phytochemicals, GC-MS.

INTRODUCTION

Reactive Oxygen Species (ROS) denote a collection of oxygen radicals (O_2^- , OH), and some derivatives of oxygen like H_2O_2 and singlet oxygen. ROS are generated during the normal metabolism of eukaryotic cells, ROS mediated oxidative damage to macromolecules namely lipids, proteins and DNA have been implicated in the pathogenicity of major diseases such as cancer, rheumatoid arthritis, post ischemic reperfusion injury, degeneration process of aging, myocardial infarction, cardiovascular disease (Shafique *et al.*, 2011; Soni & Sosa, 2013). The *Lamiaceae* is one of the most important medicinal plants containing family as a worldwide. The genus *Ocimum* comprising more than 60 species including *basilicum*. The *Ocimum basilicum* is an annual herb which grows in several regions around the world. The plant probably

originated in Indio-malaya regions and occur in Afghanistan, Pakistan, Northern India and Iran, and now is commercially cultivated worldwide (Zakaria *et al.*, 2008). The plant material was used traditionally for various ailments and has been widely utilized in food as a flavoring agent, and in perfumery and medicinal fields (Talaat & Balbaa, 2010). The tops of plant leaves and flowerings are apparent as carminative, galactogogue, stomachic and antispasmodic in folk medicine (Mohanty *et al.*, 2014). However, recently the potential uses of *O. basilicum* essential oil, particularly as antimicrobial and antioxidant potential content also have been applied for the treatment of acne, loss of smell, insect stings, snake bites, and skin infections (Martin & Ernst, 2004). The chief compounds responsible for the antimicrobial, antioxidant potential and the presence of some characteristic aroma are chavicol,

*Corresponding Author: Dr. G. Prabakaran, Assistant Professor, PG and Research department of Botany, Government Arts College, Dharmapuri, 636 705, Tamilnadu, India., Email: gpbitek@gmail.com, Mobile: +91 9442438280

methyl ether, linalool, eugenol, 1, 8-cineole and methyl cinnamate (Lee & Scagel, 2010). The non-volatile compounds were found to be rich in phenolic acids with major part of caffeic, rosmarinic acid and chicoric acids (Zlotek *et al.*, 2016). So the aim of this study is to evaluate the influence of using different solvents extraction on the antioxidant activity, qualitative phytochemical analysis and to screen the active constituents by GC-MS in *O. basilicum* from various geographical conditions.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Source of collected samples

Healthy and mature of flowering aerial parts leaves of *O. basilicum* (Lamiaceae) were collected from different ecotype habitats like hills and coastal regions of tamilnadu in India such as Valparai, Chidambaram, Yercaud, Courtallam and Ramanathapuram. The plant leaf sample was identified by renowned taxonomist and authenticated in Botanical Survey of India (BSI) Coimbatore of Tamilnadu in India. Voucher number BSI/SRC/5/23/2013-14/TECH/1287.

Preparation of extraction for analysis

The flowering aerial parts leaves (1 kg from each accession) were shade dried and ground well using mechanical blender into fine powder and transferred into airtight containers with proper labeling for future use. Methanol, Acetone, Petroleum ether, chloroform and Aqueous extract of increasing polarity were used successively for the extraction of active principles from the dried and pulverized plant using soxhlet extraction method (Adiguzel *et al.*, 2005). The extraction was continued for 72 hour, till the extraction becomes colorless and was filtered using Whatman No.1 filter paper. The extracts were concentrated at 40°C in vacuum rotary evaporator and then diluted and made up with (0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0 and 2.5 mg/ml) of same solvent for antioxidant studies.

ABTS Scavenging Effects

The antioxidant activity of all the accessions of different leaf extracts were carried out using ABTS (2,2'-azino-bis-3-ethyl benzthiazoline-6-sulphonic acid) diammonium salt radical cation decolorization assay was performed by using spectrophotometric method of (Shirwaikar *et al.*, 2006). ABTS radical cations (ABTS⁺) were formed by reacting ABTS solution (7 mM) with 2.45 mM ammonium persulphate. The mixed solution was allowed to stand in dark at room temperature for 12-16 hours. 0.5 ml of the five different extracts of all accessions was added to 0.3ml of ABTS solution and the final volume was made up to 1ml with ethanol. The absorbance was read at 745 nm in a spectrophotometer and the inhibition percent was calculated using the formula.

$$\text{Inhibition (\%)} = \frac{(\text{Control} - \text{Test}) \times 100}{\text{Control}}$$

All the tested samples were carried in triplicates. The results are presented as the mean of \pm standard deviation. The level of significance was set at $P < 0.05$.

Glutathione peroxidase

Glutathione peroxidase (GPx) was assayed according to the procedure of (Rotruck *et al.*, 1973) with some modifications. The reaction mixture consisting of 0.4 ml of 0.4 M sodium phosphate buffer (pH 7.0), 0.1 ml of 10 mM sodium azide, 0.2 ml tissue homogenized in 0.4 M buffer pH 7.0. 0.2 ml reduced glutathione, 0.1 ml of 2.5 mM H₂O₂, 0.2 ml of water and 0.5 ml of enzyme was incubated at 0, 30, 60, 90 seconds respectively. The reaction was terminated with 0.5 ml of 10% TCA and after centrifugation; 2 ml of the supernatant was added to 3 ml of phosphate buffer and 1ml of DTNB (5, 5 -dithiobisnitrobenzoic acid) reagent (0.04% DTNB in 1% sodium citrate). The color developed was read at 412 nm and the enzyme activity is expressed in terms of μg of glutathione utilized/min/mg protein. All the tested samples were carried in triplicates. The results are presented as the mean of \pm standard deviation. The level of significance was set at $P < 0.05$.

Phytochemical investigations

The preliminary phytochemical analysis for presence of phytoconstituents such as alkaloids, Flavonoids, phenols, saponins, steroids, tannins, terpenoids and glucosides. In the screening the phytochemical analysis the methanol extracts of courtallam sample were carried out qualitatively using standard procedures (Kokate *et al.*, 2001) Response of different tests was denoted by positive signs (+, ++, +++) indicates weak, moderate and strong reactions respectively and (-) indicates absent.

Preparation of Thin Layer Chromatography Plates (PTLCP)

25 g of Merck silica gel was suspended in 50 mL of deionised water and shaken vigorously for 45 seconds in rubber-stopper Erlenmeyer flask (500 mL). The thickened slurry was poured into the glass and pulled with a ruler in two sides at 1mm trailing edge to prepare similar plates. Then, the plates were allowed to air dry 30 minutes in the oven at 50°C (until they turn white). After drying, each of the plates was placed in the separate glass chamber with solvent system Hexane: acetone (9:1 v/v) and Chloroform: methanol (9:1) as the mobile phase. After the movement of solvent at the top of the plates, each plate was removed from the glass chamber and separately air-dried. After air-drying, the produced spots were located by their fluorescence under short and long wavelength of UV light (254 and 366 nm respectively).

Gas Chromatography - Mass Spectroscopy (GC-MS)

GC MS Analysis was carried out on thermo GC trace ultra ver 5.0, Thermo MS DSQ II and gas chromatograph interfaced to a mass spectrometer (GC-MS) instrument employing the following conditions. DB 5-MS capillary

standard non-polar column, Dimension-30 mts ID: 0.25 mm film 0-0.25 mm, helium was used as carrier gas at a constant flow of 1ml/min. The oven temperature was programmed from 70°C raised to 260°C/min. The eluted component is detected in the mass detector and the components were compared with components stored in the library and determined the name, molecular weight etc. Identification of phytocomponents was conducted using the database of Wiley-9 combined with the National Institute of Standard and Technology (NIST) library. The name, molecular weight, molecular formula and area under peak of the components of the test material were ascertained.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In antioxidant activity of *O. basilicum* leaves of various polar and non polar solvent extracts, all the concentrations expressed the significant inhibition of scavenging activities and the values are integrated with statistical analysis. The non enzymatic (ABTS) and enzymatic method (GPx) of antioxidant assay the amount of sample required to absorb and decolorize was plotted against the concentration in mg/ml extracts.

In the ABTS method of antioxidant activity in *O. basilicum* of different extractions the highest inhibition

percentage of ABTS was shown by all the samples synergistic property due to presence of phenol components. Table-1 shows the lowest concentration (0.5 mg/ml) of methanol and aqueous extract of Chidambaram and Yercaud samples has high inhibition percentage of free radicals (42.03 ± 0.05 and 41.96 ± 96 respectively). Similar inhibition percentage (6.33 ± 0.10 and 8.4 ± 0.50) was lowest in methanol extract of Courtallam and Valparai sample.

In the results of present investigation the enzymatic Glutathione peroxidase was observed in various habited *O. basilicum* leaves of different solvent extracts in this antioxidant assay, presence of highest activity was seen in least concentration (0.5 mg/ml) of aqueous extract of accessions (176.26 ± 0.05 units/mg protein/min) and (144.26 ± 0.05 units/mg protein/min) Ramanathapuram and Courtallam sample respectively compared to other samples followed by Acetone and methanol extract. The lowest activity in Yercaud (32.03 ± 0.57 units/mg protein/min) and Chidambaram (48.13 ± 0.11) samples in same concentration of aqueous extracts compare to Courtallam (48.40 ± 0.17) and Chidambaram (48.20 ± 0.10) in methanol extract (Table-2). It has been well established that, GPx a selenium enzyme, plays a major role in regulating the concentration of H_2O_2 and a wide variety of organic peroxides.

Table 1. The ABTS antioxidant activities of different solvent extracts of *Ocimum basilicum* leaves from various habitats.

S.No.	Samples	Con. of Samples mg/ml	Different solvent extracts				
			Acetone	Chloroform	Petroleum ether	Aqueous	Methanol
1	Valparai	0.5	25.51 ± 1.32	25.33 ± 0.57	10.70 ± 0.26	10.46 ± 0.30	6.3 ± 0.1
		1.0	37.43 ± 0.17	30.23 ± 0.25	26.00 ± 0.11	28.30 ± 0.10	22.10 ± 1.04
		1.5	55.20 ± 0.30	50.10 ± 0.10	42.20 ± 0.26	48.93 ± 0.30	48.22 ± 0.25
		2.0	72.13 ± 0.15	72.46 ± 0.35	60.16 ± 0.57	58.83 ± 0.20	67.43 ± 0.40
		2.5	80.11 ± 0.10	85.26 ± 0.28	73.16 ± 0.15	79.33 ± 0.20	77.26 ± 0.20
2	Chidambaram	0.5	12.13 ± 0.15	37.53 ± 0.05	16.0 ± 0.20	10.13 ± 0.05	42.03 ± 0.05
		1.0	41.16 ± 0.20	52.23 ± 0.25	28.10 ± 0.10	28.10 ± 0.30	55.23 ± 0.15
		1.5	63.16 ± 0.15	65.10 ± 0.10	52.13 ± 0.15	42.23 ± 2.30	67.26 ± 0.17
		2.0	81.20 ± 0.20	75.26 ± 0.15	64.16 ± 0.05	62.16 ± 0.20	79.53 ± 0.15
		2.5	95.20 ± 0.17	92.16 ± 0.20	80.23 ± 0.15	78.6 ± 0.17	88.33 ± 0.30
3	Yercaud	0.5	22.13 ± 0.15	12.13 ± 0.11	10.13 ± 0.11	41.96 ± 0.15	15.20 ± 0.20
		1.0	38.10 ± 0.10	26.00 ± 0.11	34.01 ± 0.10	54.06 ± 0.05	24.13 ± 0.05
		1.5	50.10 ± 0.10	52.06 ± 0.15	48.16 ± 0.05	67.16 ± 0.20	48.26 ± 0.20
		2.0	70.16 ± 0.20	70.20 ± 0.20	70.06 ± 0.05	75.16 ± 0.11	64.30 ± 0.26
		2.5	84.20 ± 0.10	80.33 ± 0.20	80.04 ± 0.10	96.20 ± 0.20	80.33 ± 0.32
4	Courtallam	0.5	20.30 ± 0.20	22.20 ± 0.26	25.13 ± 0.15	17.26 ± 0.20	21.50 ± 0.30
		1.0	33.40 ± 0.10	37.20 ± 0.20	37.43 ± 0.57	29.23 ± 0.20	34.63 ± 0.15
		1.5	46.20 ± 0.26	55.10 ± 0.05	50.23 ± 0.15	49.36 ± 0.15	47.33 ± 0.20
		2.0	61.13 ± 0.11	70.26 ± 0.20	62.30 ± 0.20	63.26 ± 0.20	63.36 ± 0.37
		2.5	82.16 ± 0.05	77.43 ± 0.05	80.23 ± 0.15	80.23 ± 0.17	76.43 ± 0.11
5	Ramanathapuram	0.5	20.40 ± 0.26	16.03 ± 0.15	15.40 ± 0.20	19.30 ± 0.26	8.4 ± 0.50
		1.0	37.33 ± 0.20	26.50 ± 0.26	24.20 ± 0.26	28.50 ± 0.10	23.16 ± 0.30
		1.5	48.40 ± 0.26	41.40 ± 0.26	39.46 ± 0.15	36.50 ± 0.26	40.40 ± 0.17
		2.0	60.21 ± 0.20	56.46 ± 0.30	54.43 ± 0.20	58.30 ± 0.10	54.30 ± 0.26
		2.5	77.33 ± 0.20	71.53 ± 0.05	70.16 ± 0.05	69.33 ± 0.20	78.13 ± 0.32

Values are average and represented as mean \pm standard deviation.

Table 2. Glutathione peroxidase (GPx) - antioxidant activities of different solvent extracts of *Ocimum basilicum* leaves from various habitats.

S.No.	Samples	Con of Samples mg/ml	Different solvent extracts				
			Acetone	Chloroform	Petroleum ether	Aqueous	Methanol
1	Valparai	0.5	48.3 ± 0.1	112.2 ± 0.26	96.56 ± 0.20	112.23 ± 0.20	96.63 ± 0.20
		1.0	112.33 ± 0.20	160.23 ± 0.15	160.20 ± 0.10	144.23 ± 0.25	128.26 ± 0.15
		1.5	144.16 ± 0.57	209.23 ± 0.15	209.16 ± 0.11	192.23 ± 0.15	160.26 ± 0.20
		2.0	192.13 ± 0.15	241.26 ± 0.25	252.06 ± 0.20	241.33 ± 0.25	192.30 ± 0.20
		2.5	225.13 ± 0.15	273.06 ± 0.15	289.40 ± 0.20	289.23 ± 0.11	289.33 ± 0.25
2	Chidambaram	0.5	48.13 ± 0.11	80.33 ± 0.15	48.16 ± 0.05	48.10 ± 0.1	48.20 ± 0.10
		1.0	80.23 ± 0.11	112.23 ± 0.20	128.06 ± 0.57	128.26 ± 0.15	96.33 ± 0.20
		1.5	112.50 ± 0.20	160.16 ± 0.57	160.13 ± 0.57	160.12 ± 0.57	144.06 ± 0.11
		2.0	160.13 ± 0.57	209.13 ± 0.57	192.33 ± 0.20	192.70 ± 0.36	192.43 ± 0.57
		2.5	225.26 ± 0.15	257.26 ± 0.15	257.26 ± 0.15	257.23 ± 0.30	241.26 ± 0.25
3	Yercaud	0.5	96.56 ± 0.20	80.13 ± 0.11	64.26 ± 0.05	32.03 ± 0.57	96.43 ± 0.57
		1.0	144.16 ± 0.15	144.13 ± 0.11	112.33 ± 0.15	80.26 ± 0.05	112.10 ± 0.170
		1.5	160.23 ± 0.25	176.16 ± 0.15	160.33 ± 0.15	144.30 ± 0.26	160.36 ± 0.152
		2.0	209.16 ± 0.11	209.23 ± 0.11	209.05 ± 0.57	209.76 ± 0.05	192.26 ± 0.15
		2.5	273.26 ± 0.20	258.03 ± 0.11	273.42 ± 0.20	273.90 ± 0.10	241.33 ± 0.15
4	Courtallam	0.5	96.43 ± 0.05	48.23 ± 0.05	96.56 ± 0.40	144.26 ± 0.05	48.40 ± 0.17
		1.0	144.10 ± 0.10	112.10 ± 0.17	144.30 ± 0.17	192.43 ± 0.11	80.33 ± 0.15
		1.5	209.10 ± 0.10	160.16 ± 0.05	176.33 ± 0.15	241.10 ± 0.10	112.13 ± 0.152
		2.0	257.30 ± 0.26	209.20 ± 0.20	209.20 ± 0.10	273.20 ± 0.10	144.43 ± 0.20
		2.5	289.36 ± 0.20	273.30 ± 0.20	273.10 ± 0.10	289.40 ± 0.17	285.53 ± 0.11
5	Ramanathapuram	0.5	112.10 ± 0.17	112.40 ± 0.15	112.26 ± 0.20	176.26 ± 0.05	80.26 ± 0.05
		1.0	144.20 ± 0.10	160.20 ± 0.10	160.26 ± 0.05	209.56 ± 0.57	128.23 ± 0.57
		1.5	160.46 ± 0.28	192.33 ± 0.15	209.36 ± 0.11	241.23 ± 0.57	176.36 ± 0.11
		2.0	192.36 ± 0.11	225.36 ± 0.20	241.16 ± 0.15	273.53 ± 0.11	209.46 ± 0.15
		2.5	241.30 ± 0.30	257.30 ± 0.26	273.50 ± 0.10	289.73 ± 0.23	290.01 ± 0.45

Values are average and represented as mean ± standard deviation.

The preliminary phytochemical screening may be useful in the detection of the bioactive components and subsequently may lead to drug discovery and development. Analyzation of phytochemical screening was performed and detected the indication of active components from the methanol extract of *O.basilicum* leaves in courtallam sample. It also revealed the presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, terpenoids at moderate concentrations, polyphenols at strong concentration, saponins and steroids at weak levels. The extract showed negative result with glycosides and tannin tests marking the absence of these compounds (Table -3). In the result of Thin Layer Chromatography the different solvent systems were tried as mobile phase, of which Chloroform: methanol (9:1) gave clearly visible spots. The Rf value 0.34, 0.48, 0.55, 0.64, 0.76 and 0.92 respectively which indicates that plant *O. basilicum* indicates adequate amount of polyphenol and their derivatives may be prove whereas the Chloroform:

methanol (9:1) mobile phase used.

The results of Gas Chromatography- Mass Spectroscopy Analysis in fractions from TLC methanol solvent extraction of *Ocimum basilicum* from courtallam sample found to have qualitatively more than ten bioactive compounds (table-4) based on the order of their retention time. 2-Hydroxy- cyclopenta-2,4-dienone, 2,3-Dimethoxy-succinic acid di methyl ester, Linalool, (2-Methyl-thiiranyl)-methanol, Tetradecane, 1-(4-Methoxy-cyclohexyl) -hex-5-en-1-one, 2-tert - Butyl- 1, 2- dimethylcyclopropane, carboxylic acid methyl ester, 1-hexadecene, Caffeic acid, 2-Phenoxy-sulfonyl-acetimidic acid methyl ester, hydrochloride, 2-Allyl-5a-hydroxy-octahydro-5-oxa-2-azacyclopenta inden-1-one, 1,1-Diethoxy-2-methyl-propane, 2-Methoxyimino-4-methyl-pentanoic acid benzyl ester (Table-4).

Table 3. Qualitative analysis of secondary metabolites of methanol extracts of *Ocimum basilicum* of Courtallam sample.

S.No	Name of compound	Positive	Negative
1	Alkaloids (Hager's test)	++	
2	Flavonoids	++	
3	Phenol compounds	+++	
4	Tannins		-
5	Steroids	+	
6	Terpenoids (Salkowski's test)	++	
7	Saponin	+	
8	Glucosides (Keller Killiani test)		-

(+++)
(++) strong, (++) moderate, (+) weak, (-) absent.

Table 4. Chemical composition of *Ocimum basilicum* methanol extracts of courtallam sample.

S. No.	RT	Compound Name	Molecular Formula (M.F)	Molecular Weight (M.W)	Biological activity
1.	4.45	2-Hydroxy- cyclopenta-2,4-dienone	C ₅ H ₆ O ₂	98	Phytochemistry, Pharmaceutical Applications
2.	6.41	2,3-Dimethoxy-succinicacid dimethyl ester	C ₈ H ₁₄ O ₆	206	Antimicrobial, Cytotoxicity and Phytochemical Application
3.	6.96	Linalool	C ₁₀ H ₁₈ O	154	Biological Activity
4.	7.19	(2-Methyl-thiiranyl)-methanol	C ₄ H ₈ OS	104	Biological Studies
5.	8.10	Tetradecane	C ₁₄ H ₃₀	198	Phytochemical Constituents, Antimicrobial & Isolation
6.	11.75	1-(4-Methoxy-cyclohexyl)-hex-5-en-1-one	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ O	204	Antibacterial Studies
7.	13.24	2-tert-Butyl-1,2-dimethylcyclopropane,carboxylic acid methyl ester	C ₁₁ H ₂₀ O ₂	184	Brest Cancer & pharmaceutical Application
8.	13.45	1-hexadecene	C ₁₆ H ₃₂	224	Pharmaceutical Applications
9.	14.20	Caffeic acid	C ₉ H ₈ O ₄	180	Anticancer Activity & Biological Activity
10.	16.32	2-Phenoxy-sulfonyl-acetimidic acid methyl ester, hydrochloride	C ₉ H ₁₂ ClNO ₄ S	265	Phytochemical Screening
11.	20.84	2-Allyl-5a-hydroxy-octahydro-5-oxa-2-azacyclopenta[c]inden-1-one	C ₁₃ H ₁₉ NO ₃	237	Synthesis & Characterization
12.	24.16	1,1-Diethoxy-2-methyl-propane	C ₈ H ₁₈ O ₂	146	Synthesis & Biological Activity
13.	29.94	2-Methoxyimino-4-methyl-pentanoic acid benzyl ester	C ₁₄ H ₁₉ NO ₃	249	Fungicidal Activity

In similar findings of ABTS assay the plant *O.basilicum* has highest antioxidant capacity 0.825% followed by *O. sanctum* but comparatively DPPH assay was much lower (Sailaja & Shaker, 2010). ABTS Decolourization assay radical cation inactivation of free radicals various concentration of 50 to 250µg/ml Ethyl acetate extracts of *Anisomeles malabarica* IC₅₀ value was 91.06 µg/mL better than the synthetic antioxidant BHT (Vijayalakshmi & Ranganathan, 2011). The free radicals scavenging activity

utilized the protein in glutathione peroxidase was observed to be low in orange and gooseberry (424.48 - 443.13 units/mg protein), while the activity increased by two fold in tomato and four fold in grapes (Rani *et al.*, 2004). Results of phytochemical investigation was very closely related to (Jeba & Rameshkumar, 2013) who reported high level of phenol, flavonoid and reducing sugars, moderate level of tannins, Alkaloids, Quinones and mild amount of Glycosides presence in *Ocimum* species. The quantity of

phenolic compounds, particularly flavonoids and tannins have considerably increased in recent years because of their broad spectrum of chemical and diverse biological properties which include the antioxidant effects and radical scavenging properties (Zakaria, 2007).

Similar finding was observed in TLC lemon basil revealed the presence of phenols and terpenes when the plate was developed in toluene: ethyl acetate (19:1) (Tahira *et al.*, 2013). Methanol extracts of *O.basilicum* the solvent system, Toluene: Chloroform: Ethanol (4:4:1) exhibit excellent 12 bands and different Rf values observed when sulphuric acid spray reagent viewed under UV at 254 and 366nm (Ramakrishna *et al.*, 2012). High level of monoterpene, caffeic acid and linalool were found during the qualitative analysis by GC-MS that are the major components responsible for higher antioxidant activity (Chaleshtori *et al.*, 2015; Keita *et al.*, 2000). Zhang, Li, & Wu, (2009) reported the main components present in *Ocimum basilicum* like linalool (29.68%), Z- cinnamic acid methyl ester (21.49%), cyclohexane (4.41%), alpha-cadinol (3.99%), 2,4-diisopropenyl-1-methyl-1-vinylcyclohexane(2.27%), 3,5-pyridine- dicarboxylic acid, 2,6-dimethyl-diethyl ester, beta-cubebene, guaia-1(10), 11-diene, cadinene, (E) cinnamic acid methyl ester and beta-guaiene. There was a strong relationship between the phenolic content and the antioxidant activity expressed (Juliani & Simon, 2002). These results suggest that the antioxidant activity in basil is largely due to the phenolic components.

CONCLUSION

The present study concludes that the ABTS and GPx methods of antioxidants activity performed in various extracts of all the habitat samples of *O. basilicum* the highest inhibition percentage was seen in the methanolic extracts compared to other extracts. Preliminary phytochemical screening showed the presence of polyphenol, alkaloids and flavonoids whereas glycosides and tannins were found to be absent. In qualitative analysis of GC-MS, Linalool, caffeic acid and more bioactive components were found in *O. basilicum* that has greater influence on antioxidant activity and are based on the environmental factors like soil nature, Climate and geographical conditions.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors express sincere thanks to the head of the PG and Research department of Botany, Government Arts College, Dharmapuri for the facilities provided to carry out this research work.

REFERENCES

Adiguzel, A., Gulluce, M., Şengul, M., Ogutcu, H., Şahin, F., & Karaman, I. (2005). Antimicrobial effects of

Ocimum basilicum (Labiatae) extract. *Turkish Journal of Biology*, 29(3), 155-160.

Chaleshtori, S., Rokni, N., Rafieian Kopaei, M., Deris, F., & Salehi, E. (2015). Antioxidant and antibacterial activity of basil (*Ocimum basilicum* L.) essential oil in beef burger. *Journal of Agricultural Science and Technology*, 17(4), 817-826.

Jeba, R.C., & Rameshkumar, G. (2013). Antimicrobial activity of *Ocimum* species. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Science and Health Care*, 3(3), 9-11.

Juliani, H., & Simon, J. (2002). Antioxidant activity of basil. *Trends in New Crops and New Uses*, 1-575.

Keita, S. M., Vincent, C., Schmit, J. P., & Belanger, A. (2000). Essential oil composition of *Ocimum basilicum* L., *O. gratissimum* L. and *O. suave* L. in the Republic of Guinea. *Flavour and Fragrance Journal*, 15(5), 339-341.

Kokate, C., Purohit, A., & Gokhale, S. (2001). Carbohydrate and derived Products, drugs containing glycosides, drugs containing tannins, lipids and protein alkaloids. *Text book of Pharmacognosy*, 7, 133-166.

Lee, J., & Scagel, C.F. (2010). Chicoric acid levels in commercial basil (*Ocimum basilicum*) and Echinacea purpurea products. *Journal of Functional Foods*, 2(1), 77-84.

Martin, K.W., & Ernst, E. (2004). Herbal medicines for treatment of fungal infections: a systematic review of controlled clinical trials. *Mycoses*, 47(3-4), 87-92.

Mohanty, B., Mahanty, A., Ganguly, S., Sankar, T., Chakraborty, K., Rangasamy, A., Asha, K.K. (2014). Amino acid compositions of 27 food fishes and their importance in clinical nutrition. *Journal of Amino Acids*, 2014,1-7.

Ramakrishna, K., Sampath, S., Chacko, J., Chacko, B., Narahari, D.L., Veerendra, H. H., Raju, R. K. (2012). Clinical profile and predictors of mortality of severe pandemic (H1N1) 2009 virus infection needing intensive care: a multi-centre prospective study from South India. *Journal of Global Infectious Diseases*, 4(3), 145-151.

Rani, P., Unni, K. M., & Karthikeyan, J. (2004). Evaluation of antioxidant properties of berries. *Indian Journal of Clinical Biochemistry*, 19(2), 103-109.

Rotruck, J., Pope, A., Ganther, H.E., Swanson, A., Hafeman, D.G., & Hoekstra, W. (1973). Selenium: biochemical role as a component of glutathione peroxidase. *Science*, 179(4073), 588-590.

Sailaja, I., & Shaker, I. (2010). Antioxidant activity in *Ocimum sanctum* Linn, *Ocimum basilicum*. *Asian Journal of Bio Science*, 5(2), 195-199.

Shafique, M., Khan, S.J., & Khan, N. H. (2011). Study of antioxidant and antimicrobial activity of sweet basil

- (*Ocimum basilicum*) essential oil. *Pharmacologyonline*, 1, 105-111.
- Shirwaikar, A., Shirwaikar, A., Rajendran, K., & Punitha, I. S. R. (2006). In vitro antioxidant studies on the benzyl tetra isoquinoline alkaloid berberine. *Biological and Pharmaceutical Bulletin*, 29(9), 1906-1910.
- Soni, A., & Sosa, S. (2013). Phytochemical analysis and free radical scavenging potential of herbal and medicinal plant extracts. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry*, 2(4), 22-29.
- Tahira, R., Rehan, T., & Ata-ur-Rehman, N.M. (2013). Variation in bioactive compounds in different parts of lemon basil (*Ocimum Basilicum* var. *citriodorum*). *The Experimental*, 17(2), 1184-1190.
- Talaat, I. M., & Balbaa, L.K. (2010). Physiological response of sweet basil plants (*Ocimum basilicum* L.) to putrescine and trans cinnamic acid. *American Eurasian Journal of Agricultural and Environmental Science*, 8(4), 438-445.
- Vijayalakshmi, R., & Ranganathan, R. (2011). Antimicrobial activity of various extracts of whole plant of *Anisomeles malabarica* (Linn.) R. Br. *International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 1(2), 73-79.
- Zakaria, Z., Aziz, R., Lachimanan, Y. L., Sreenivasan, S., & Rathinam, X. (2008). Antioxidant activity of *Coleus blumei*, *Orthosiphon stamineus*, *Ocimum basilicum* and *Mentha arvensis* from Lamiaceae family. *Int J Nat Eng Sci*, 2(1), 93-95.
- Zakaria, Z.A. (2007). Free radical scavenging activity of some plants available in Malaysia. *Iranian Journal of Pharmacology and Therapeutics*, 6(1), 87-80.
- Zhang, J.W., Li, S.K., & Wu, W.J. (2009). The main chemical composition and in vitro antifungal activity of the essential oils of *Ocimum basilicum* Linn. var. *pilosum* (Willd.) Benth. *Molecules*, 14(1), 273-278.
- Złotek, U., Mikulska, S., Nagajek, M., & Swieca, M. (2016). The effect of different solvents and number of extraction steps on the polyphenol content and antioxidant capacity of basil leaves (*Ocimum basilicum* L.) extracts. *Saudi Journal of Biological Sciences*, 23(5), 628-633.